

Horizon 2020_ME-WE_Psychosocial Support for Promoting Mental Health and Well-being among Adolescent Young Carers in Europe_Ref. Nr. 754702/9331

WP 2 - National policy, legal and service frameworks

Final List of Experts in Six Countries (agreed on between the SKF team and the partner countries)

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1 Experts in Italy

	Name and sur-name	Position	Main expertise	For details/contacts
1	Raffaele Focaroli	Pedagogist, Tribunal of minors – Rome	Children's rights	
2	Alfredo Ferrante	Official - Coordinator for the promotion of services for the family, international and community relations, Department of family policies; Italian Presidency of the Council of Ministers	Children's rights	
3	Loredana Ligabue	Anziani e non Solo, Associazione Carer	She worked bottom-up at the first regional law in Emilia Romagna (legge regionale 28 marzo 2014, n. 2) that acknowledges family caregivers and at Ignazio Angioni's national law proposal for the acknowledgement and valorisation of the family caregiver.	
4	Benedetta Piola Caselli	Lawyer	Children's rights	

2 Experts in Netherlands

	Name and surname	Position	Main expertise	For details/contacts
1	Prof. Dr. Margrite Kalverboer	Associate professor (Child(Ortho)pedagogics and Child- and foreign rights, because of Stichting Groninger Universiteitsfonds	<p>Youth care, underage asylum seekers, children's rights;</p> <p>Kalverboer has been appointed as the new Dutch Child Ombudsman in April 2016.</p> <p>Lawyer with focus on children and national ombudsman for children</p>	<p>https://www.rug.nl/staff/m.e.kalverboer/</p> <p>Contact +31 50 36 36571 +31 800 876 5432 m.e.kalverboer@rug.nl</p> <p>https://www.nationaleombudsman.nl/nieuws/2016/margrite-kalverboer-sworn-as-ombudsman-for-children-0</p>
2	Dr. A.N.D. (Anne-Marie) Huyghen And Jana Knot-Dickscheit	University of Groningen Faculty of Behavioural and Social Sciences	<p>Young carers and the Need for Interdisciplinary Cooperation</p> <p>School absenteeism/school truancy</p> <p>Field/Discipline</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Behavioural Sciences - Education, Special - Psychology, Developmental <p>Expertise Special education and youth care</p>	<p>https://www.rug.nl/staff/a.m.n.huyghen/research</p> <p>Contact: +31 50 36 36788 a.m.n.huyghen@rug.nl</p>
3	Anjet van Dijken		<p>Masters degree in Dutch law, worked at a national policy in the Netherlands, and is the author of a book on having a brother or sister with a chronic illness.</p> <p>Journalist en schrijver Anjet van Dijken (1976) groeide op met</p>	<p>ANJET VAN DIJKEN Kloktorenstraat 44 1040 Brussel België M +32 4 68218232</p> <p>E anjetxt@gmail.com W www.brussenboek.nl/be</p>

	Name and surname	Position	Main expertise	For details/contacts
			haar drie jaar oudere broer met een visuele en verstandelijke handicap.	
4	Prof. Dr. Mariëlle Bruning	Professor of Children and the law University Leiden	Child Abuse, child law, child protection, children's rights, juvenile justice, youth care	https://www.universiteitleiden.nl/en/staffmembers/marielle-bruning?#tab-1 Contact +31 71 527 8913 m.r.bruning@law.leidenuniv.nl

3 Experts in Slovenia

	Name and surname	Position	Main expertise	For details/contacts
1	Ass. prof. dr. Tomaž Deželan	Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Ljubljana, expert for youth policy	Areas of expertise: citizenship concepts, debates and regimes, new models of governance, parliamentary cohesion, electoral studies, youth, gender and civil society.	
2	Barbara Zupan	Office of the Republic of Slovenia for Youth		E: barbarazupan@gov.si T: + 386 1 426 5701
3	Ružica Boškić	Secretary, Member of the Ad hoc Committee for the Rights of the Child; member of the Expert group	Child protection and family policies	

	Name and sur-name	Position	Main expertise	For details/contacts
		on the rights of the child on EC, DG Just, Ministry of Labour, Family, Social Affairs and Equal Opportunities.		
4	Davor Dominkuš	Secretary at the Ministry of Labor, Family, Social Affairs and equal opportunities		E: davor.dominkus@gov.si

4 Experts in Sweden

	Name and sur-name	Position	Main expertise	For details/contacts
1	Pernilla Häglund Leviner	Docent at the university of Stockholm, law department [LAW]	“My research interests lie within and across the fields of public and family law – more specifically child law and social welfare law. It deals with different aspects of the relation between the state, the family and the individual, including children’s rights often focusing on the responsibility and role of public authorities”.	Tel: 08 16 32 89 E-Mail: pernilla.leviner@juridicum.su.se Website: https://www.su.se/profiles/plevi-1.184442
2	Merike Hansson	National Board of Health and Welfare	Program Officer Children as Next of Kin.	Tel: 075-247-31-71

	Name and sur-name	Position	Main expertise	For details/contacts
		Sweden [POLICY]	Also suggestend by Country-Partners Sweden	E-Mail: merike.hansson@socialstyrelsen.se Website: http://www.socialstyrelsen.se/stodtillanhoriga/stod-till-barn-som-ar-anhoriga
3	Annika Remaeus	Ministry of Social Affairs		
4	Elisabet Näsman	Senior professor in Sociology University of Uppsala [RESEARCH]	She is a researcher in Childhood Sociology, focusing for the last decades on children in families where the parents have problems. Her aim is to promote an understanding of children as actors in their own life and the participatory rights this calls for.	Tel: 018 471 10 39 E-Mail: elisabet.nasman@soc.uu.se Website: http://katalog.uu.se/empinfo/?id=AA267

5 Experts in Switzerland

	Name and sur-name	Position	Main expertise	For details/contacts
1	Sandra Stössel	Amt für Jugend und Berufsberatung – Fachstelle Kinder-, Jugend- und Familienfragen ZH	Law expert	sandra.stoessel@ajb.zh.ch +41 43 259 96 58 ajb@ajb.zh.ch (general e-mail address)
2	Dr. Regula Ricka	Bundesamt für Gesundheit and	Expert and lecturer at the BAG and the University of Basel for	

	Name and sur-name	Position	Main expertise	For details/contacts
		University Basel	Health Science	
3	Prof. Dr. iur. Margot Michel	University Zurich	Expert for family law and medical law.	
4	Prof. Dr. phil. Annie Oulevey Bachmann	Institute of Health (HES), University of Lausanne	Head of the institute of Health (HES) at the university of Lausanne	

6 Experts in UK

England				
	Name and sur-name	Position	Main expertise	For details/contacts
1	Luke Clements	http://www.lukeclements.co.uk/	<p>Luke Clements is the Cerebra Professor of Law and Social Justice at the School of Law, Leeds University.</p> <p>He has helped draft and promote a number of Parliamentary Bills aimed at improving the rights of people experiencing social exclusion – including Bills that became the Carers (Recognition and Services) Act 1995 and the Carers (Equal Opportunities) Act 2004. In 2013 he was the Special Adviser to the Parliamentary Committee that scrutinised the draft Bill that resulted in the Care Act 2014.</p>	L.J.Clements@leeds.ac.uk
2	Jo Aldridge	Professor Jo Aldridge, Director and co-founder of the Young Carers; Research Group (YCRG) at Loughborough:	<p>Jo has carried out a wealth of research on young carers since the early 1990s : https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=Mbr0-usAAAAJ&hl=en</p> <p>In 2014, the Department for Education commissioned Professor Aldridge in partnership with Kantar Public to undertake a suite of research which aimed to serve as a baseline study of the lives of young carers in England: https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/the-lives-of-young-carers-in-england</p>	J.Aldridge@lboro.ac.uk

		http://www.ycrg.org.uk/		
3	Helen Leadbitter	Operational Manager for the Include Project, The Children's Society.	Helen has worked in the field of young carers development and policy for about 18 years. Helen wrote: Leadbitter, H. Whole Family Pathway. 2015. London: The Children's Society. Helen co-lead Making a Step Change for Young Carers and their Families: Putting it into practice (2015-2016) a partnership project between Carers Trust and The Children's Society to support the effective implementation by local authorities of the duties required under the Care Act 2014 and the Children and Families Act 2014 with regard to young carers and their families.	Hel-en.Leadbitter@childrensociety.org.uk
4	Maurice Leeson	Government sector leader, Children and Young People's Strategic Partnership (Northern Ireland)		
5	Louise Morgan	Carers Trust	https://carers.org/carers-trust-spokespeople Louise Morgan, Development Manager (Young Carers - Scotland) Louise works with all the young carers' projects in Scotland and with the Scottish Government to develop new services and legislation to support young carers. She can speak about every aspect of issues affecting young carers.	lmorgan@carers.org